

SYNTHESIS AND CHARACTERIZATION OF VEGETABLE OIL-BASED POLYOL FROM JATROPHA CURCAS (EUPHORBIACEAE) SEED OIL

Okoye, S.I., Waziri, A.Y., Mohammed, A. and Abubakar, A.M.

Department of Chemical Engineering, Faculty of Engineering, Adamawa State, Nigeria

Corresponding email: yusufabubakarwaziri@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Polyols are traditionally produced from petroleum. However, the production of polyols from petrochemicals is costly, requires a great deal of energy and also has adverse effects on the environment. Recent investigations show that in recent years the focus on alternatives petrochemicals-based polyols, non-petroleum-based sources of polyols that are renewable, less costly, and more ecofriendly became necessary. This experiment therefore sets out to synthesize biobased based polyol from Jatropha curcas (Euphorbiaceae) seed oil as a way of substituting polyol from petroleum derivatives. Jatropha curcas (Euphorbiaceae) oil was extracted from its oil-bearing seeds by hot water method of extraction at a temperature of 80°C, And the polyol will be produced using epoxidation and hydroxidation reaction. The oil was characterized and the oil yield, refractive index, acid value, saponification value, peroxide value, iodine value and viscosity were found to be: 51% w/v, 1.4770, 0.2805 mg/KOH/g, 196.9mg/KOH, 30mg/kH, 149.8mg/100g, 227.58Cp respectively. The oil was epoxidized at 40°C using performic acid and formic acids. The epoxidized oil was characterized and the acid value, saponification value, refractive index and iodine value were found to be; 35.03, 105.90, 1.396 and 19.65 respectively. The epoxidized oil was used to synthesize a polyol by hydroxylation process. The viscosity of the polyol was found to be 48.26 and a hydroxyl value of 156.0. These make it suitable for the manufacturing of flexible polyurethane foams. The results obtained show that, the oil which is a renewable raw material has a potential in replacing the non-renewable petroleum based raw materials in the synthesis of polyol of industrial importance.

Keywords: Jatropha seed oil, Synthesis, Polyol, Vegetable Oil-base

1 INTRODUCTION

Recently bio-based renewable resources for use in the production of useful chemicals and new materials has grown rapidly during the past few years. This is motivated by the potential advantages offered by the bio-based resources, in environment compatibility and economic feasibility, as compared to the traditional petrochemical derivatives [1]. Polyurethane foams have a high degree of versatility due to the many ways they can be applied in the production of a wide range of materials which are used differently in domestic and industrial applications. Its production involves the step-growth polymerization of a polyisocyanate of functionality 2.7 with a polyalcohol (polyol) of molecular weights from 2000–10000 and functionality 2 to 3, followed by the blowing reaction of two parts polyisocyanate with one-part water in the presence of an amine and tin compound catalysts and other additives. The global consumption of polyurethane foams was above 7 million metric tons in the year 2007, and the average

annual growth rate is about 5% [2]. This polyhydroxyl compound called Polyol, is an important building block of polyurethanes and polyesters. Generally, polyols are traditionally produced from petroleum. However, the production of polyols from petrochemicals is costly, requires a great deal of energy and also has adverse effects on the environment [3]. Polyols can be produced by two consecutive reactions namely, epoxidation and hydroxylation [4]. During the epoxidation reaction, the double oil in the vegetable oil is converted to epoxide (oxirane groups). In the second stage of the reaction hydroxylation occurs. Here, the epoxide groups are converted to hydroxyl groups and the resulting product is a polyol as it contains more than one hydroxyl groups. Recent investigations show that in recent years the focus on alternatives petrochemicals-based polyols, non-petroleum-based sources of polyols that are renewable, less costly, and more ecofriendly [5] became necessary. These bio-polyols synthesized from vegetable oils proved to be an alternative for this purpose and has therefore drawn considerable current attention. Vegetable oils such as sunflower, canola, corn, olive, palm and soy oils are being explored for the synthesis of polyols. The vegetable oil molecules must however, be chemically transformed to introduce hydroxyl groups for formation of polyols [6, 7]. However, far too little attention has been paid to the utilization of Tsada seed oil (*Ximenia americana*) seed oil, the epoxidation and hydroxylation reactions have been optimized to obtain a high quality of polyol since different raw materials will have different characteristics. High quality of polyol is indicated by high content of hydroxyl groups represented by hydroxyl value. This polyol could find applications in thermoset and thermoplastic materials, adhesives and rigid or non-rigid foams [8]. This experiment therefore sets out to synthesize bio based polyol from *Jatropha curcas* (Euphorbiaceae) seed oil as a way of substituting polyol from petroleum derivatives.

2 MATERIALS AND METHOD

2.1 Sample collection and Preparation

Jatropha curcas (euphorbiaceae) seeds were collected from Toungo (II) village in Song local government area of Adamawa State, Nigeria. The seeds were sun dried and then oven dried at 45°C to constant weight and ground with porcelain mortar and piston to coarse particle size and stored in plastic containers for analysis.

2.2 Experimental procedure

The epoxidation *Jatropha curcas* (euphorbiaceae) seed oil was carried out with the use of peracetic acid and performic acid, generated directly in the environment of the reaction as a result of the reaction of 30 wt% solution of hydrogen peroxide and acetic or performic acid respectively [9].

2.3 Extraction of *Jatropha Curcas* (euphorbiaceae) Seed Oil

The oil was extracted using hot water method for four hours [3]. Characterization of the *Jatropha curcas* (euphorbiaceae) seed oil was carried out for the following values: refractive index value, acid value, saponification value, peroxide value, iodine value and the viscosity were determined using the method described by Association of Official Agricultural Chemists [2, 10].

2.4 Hydroxylation of Epoxidized *Jatropha curcas* (euphorbiaceae) seed oil

The hydroxylation of the epoxidized oil to yield the polyol was done by adding the oil, which is in the solvent, to a mixture of an alcohol, water with H₂SO₄ acid as a catalyst for the reaction to form the vegetable oil-based polyol. The calculation of chemicals required for the hydroxylation reaction using a mixture of alcohol (methanol and isopropanol) and water with H₂SO₄ acid as a catalyst for the reaction to form the vegetable oil-based polyol. Based on the literature, a typical fatty acid composition profile [11] for *X. americana* seed oil is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Fatty acid composition and their molecular weights present in *X. americana* seed oil

Fatty acids	Molecular Weight	Composition (wt%)	Molecular weight (g/mol)
Linoleic	(C ₁₈ H ₃₂ O ₂)	1.34	280.5
Linolenic	(C ₁₈ H ₃₀ O ₂)	10.31	278.43
Arachidonic	(C ₂₀ H ₃₂ O ₂)	0.60	304.47
Eicosatrienoic	(C ₂₀ H ₃₄ O ₂)	3.39	306.48
Erucic	(C ₂₀ H ₄₂ O ₂)	3.46	338.57
Nervonic	(C ₂₄ H ₄₆ O ₂)	1.23	366.62
Oleic	(C ₁₈ H ₃₄ O ₂)	72.09	282.46

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The physicochemical properties of *Jatropha curcas* (euphorbiaceae) seed oil is shown in Table 2. From Table 2, the oil yield was found to be 51%w/v. The yield shows its potential in the manufacture of oleochemicals. The iodine value of 92.46 mg/100g indicated that the oil is non-drying oil, consisting predominantly of polysaturated fatty acids, with a potential in production of soap [5].

Table 2. Physicochemical Properties of (*Jatropha*) Seed Oil

Property	Value
Oil yield	51% w/v
Refractive index	1.4770
Acid value (mg/KOH)	0.2805
Saponification value(mg/KOH)	196.9
peroxide value (mg/KH)	30mgEuiv/kg
Iodine value	92.46 mg/100g,
Viscosity(cP)	227.58Cp @25 °C

The saponification value of the oil was found to be 196.9mg/KOH. Saponification value indicates the average molecular weight of the oil [12]. A high saponification value indicates that the oil contained higher proportions of low molecular weight fatty acids. Acid value was found to be 0.2805. Acid value of oil measures the extent to which the glycerides had been decomposed by lipase action. The decomposition is usually accelerated by heat and light. The acids that are usually formed include free fatty acids, acid phosphate and amino acids. Free fatty acids are formed at a faster rate than the other acids [13]. The peroxide value is the measure of oxidative rancidity of oil. Oxidative rancidity is the addition of oxygen across the double bonds in unsaturated fatty acids in the presence of enzyme or certain chemical compounds. The odour and flavour associated with rancidity are due to liberation of short chain carboxylic acids. High peroxide values are associated with high rate of rancidity. Variation of peroxide value could be due to the number of unsaturated fatty acid content, since the rate of oxidation of fats and oils increases with increasing level of unsaturation. The low peroxide value of 4.12 indicates that it is less liable to oxidative rancidity at room temperature. The viscosity of the oil was found to be 227.58Cp and the refractive of 1.4770 all conforms to the values given by literature for other vegetable oils. This is an indication that the oil extracted was of high degree of purity. The results for the epoxidation of Americana seed oil are presented in Table 3. The refractive index of 1.396 of the epoxidized is lower than that of the extracted oil of 1.4770, due to decrease in the degree of unsaturation occasioned by epoxidation, since refractive indices increase with degree of unsaturation. The acid value of epoxidized oil of 15.5 is higher than that of the extracted oil of 0.2805. This could be due to structural residue formed during epoxidation, since acid value is found to increase with free fatty acid and structural residue. The saponification value of the epoxidized oil of 107.05 is lower than that of the extracted oil of 196.9, due to increase in the molecular weight of epoxidized oil since molecular weight decreases with increasing saponification value. The iodine value of 125.5 of the

epoxidized oil is lower than that of the extracted oil of 149.8. This could be due to decrease in the degree of unsaturation, cause by epoxidation.

Table 3. Physicochemical Properties of Epoxidized (*Jatropha curcas*) Seed Oil

Property	Value
Acid value	15.5mg/KOH/g
Saponification value	107.05 mg/KOH
Refractive index	1.396
Iodine value	125.5 mg/KOH

Table 4 shows the result of characterization of the polyol formed from the hydroxylation process. The viscosity of the polyol was found to be 46.48 and the hydroxyl value of 156.0 makes it suitable in the manufacture of flexible polyurethane.

Table 4. showing properties of polyol produced

Property	Value
Viscosity	46.48cP
Hydroxyl value	156.0 mg/g

The FTIR spectrum of polyol Figure 1, shows the broad band stretching at 3402.54 cm^{-1} reveals the presence of $-\text{OH}$ group, 1718.53 cm^{-1} stretching is attributed to carbonyl units of ester linkage, 2934.79 cm^{-1} corresponds to asymmetric stretching of $-\text{CH}$ of adipic acid and hexanediol [14]. These peaks are also present in the tsada seed oil-based polyol which confirms the authenticity of the vegetable polyol. The difference is the presence of peak at 2342.97 cm^{-1} which appears in the petroleum polyol spectrum, this indicates the presence of other $-\text{CH}$ bonds in the commercial polyol. Also, broader band in the *Jatropha curcas* (euphorbiaceae) seed oil polyol is probably due to the presence of H_2O in the sample [6, 14].

Figure 1. Showing FTIR of polyol from *Jatropha* seed oil (b) with the commercial polyester polyol (A)

4 CONCLUSIONS

The oil yield of *Jatropha curcas* (euphorbiaceae) seed oil of 51.1wt% is good and shows its potentials in the manufacture of oleochemicals. The polyol formed by the hydroxylation of the epoxidized *Jatropha curcas* (euphorbiaceae) seed oil with a viscosity of 46.48cP and a hydroxyl value of 156.0 mg/g,

establishes its suitability in the manufacture of flexible polyurethane. These results indicated that the oil which is a renewable raw material has a potential in replacing the non-renewable petroleum based raw materials in the synthesis of polyol of industrial importance.

REFERENCES

1. Alper, H., Garcia, J.L. and Jang, E.J. (2002). New heterogeneous catalysis for the synthesis of poly (ether polyol). *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, vol. 86, no. 7, pp. 1553-1557.
2. Kaszynski, P., Oleg, K., Karol, O. and Thomas, A.B. (2003). Polyester Polyols: Synthesis and Characterization of Diethylene Glycol Terephthalate Oligomers. *Journal of Polymer Science: Part A: Polymer Chemistry*, vol. 41, no. 8, pp. 1114-1123.
3. Narayan, R., Phuong, T., and Daniel, G., Rios, L.A., Weckes, P., Schuster, H. and Hoedrich, W.F. (2005). Mesoporous and amorphous Ti – silicates on the epoxidation of vegetable oils, *J. Catal.*, vol. 232, pp. 19-26.
4. Petrovic, M., Barcelo, D. and Gonzalez, S. (2003). Analysis and Removal of Emerging Contaminants in Waste Water and Drinking Water: *TrAC Trends in Analytical Chemistry*, vol. 22, no. 10, pp. 685-696.
5. Groud, V.V., Patwardhan, A.V. and Pradhan, N.C. (2006). Studies on the epoxidation of muhua oil (madhumica indica) by hydrogen peroxide, *Bioresource Technology*, vol. 97, pp. 1365-1371.
6. Okoye, S.I., Kefas, H.M., Abubakar, M.A. and Idama, E.A. (2021). Development of Bio-Based Foam from *Ximenia americana* Seed Oil Polyol: Studies on the Effect of Water Level on Some Properties of the Foam. *FUW Trends in Science & Technology Journal*, vol. 6, no. 3, 849-852.
7. Del Rio, E., Ronda, J.C., Galia, M., Lligadas, G. and Cadiz, V. (2009). Biobased segmented polyurethanes from methyl oleate based polyether polyols. *2nd Workshop on Fats and Oils as Renewable Feedstock for the Chemical Industry*. Emden. March 22-24.
8. Guo, Z., Dirmeyer, P.A., Hu, Z.Z., Gao, X. and Zhao, M. (2006). Evaluation of the second global soil wetness project soil moisture simulations: 2. sensitivity to external meteorological forcing. *Journal of Geophysical Research*, vol. 111(D22), pp. 1-11. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2006jd007845>.
9. Rohaeti, E., Suharto, S., Kristianingrum, C.F.P. (2006). Laporan Penelitian FMIPA UNY Yogyakarta.
10. Association of Official Analytical Chemists (2008). Official Method of Analysis of the Association of Official Analytical Chemists (AOAC) 18th Edition. *Association of Official Analytical Chemists Washington D.C.*
11. Eromosele, C.O. and Eromosele, I.C. (2002). Fatty acid compositions of seed oils of *Haemotostaphisbarteri* and *Ximenia americana*. *Bioresour. Technol.*, vol. 82, no. 3, pp. 303-304.
12. Eromosele, I.C., Eromosele, C.O., Innazo, P. and Njerim, P. (1993). Studies on some seeds and seed oils. *Bioresour. Technol.*, vol. 64, pp. 245-247.
13. Ekpa, O.D. and Ekpa, U.J. (1996). Comparison of the Characteristic parameters and deterioration properties of oils from the Tenera and Dura variety of the oil palm, *Journal of Chemical Research*, vol. 1, pp. 26-33.
14. Trost, B.T., Ian, F. and Steven, V.L. (1994). Organic Chemistry Vol. 7, Pergamon Press, USA. Pearson D. *The Chemical Analysis of Foods, 11th Ed., Church – hill.*